

The Impact of New Liquid Dielectric in Power Transformer on the Location and Detection of Partial Discharge Using UHF Sensors

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Abstract—In this paper, to obtain more relevant information for partial discharge (PD) diagnosis and location in the case of two different liquid dielectrics (mineral oil (MO) and natural ester (NE)), simulations are conducted using two power transformer models equipped with models of four ultra-high frequency (UHF) sensors and a PD source created with the Ansys HFSS software. This paper investigates and explains the changes and differences in the first peaks (FPs), extreme amplitudes (EAs), initial delays, waveforms, weighted mean amplitudes, and weighted mean frequency shifts of UHF PD signals at four UHF sensors in the particular periods of 12.179 ns from the FPs and from the FPs until the ends of the signals' records at 45 ns, because of their different propagation paths and attenuations in the power transformer; it also determines and explains the location of the PD source using the FP method in proposed cases of two different liquid dielectrics in the power transformer model. Also, the influences of reflected waves from the transformer's metal parts on the signals at the UHF sensors are analysed. When comparing the NE model to the MO model, the FPs and EAs in the first wave packets of signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 at the corresponding sensors are, on average, 1.88 times and 1.28 times larger. The dipole antenna's (serving as a source and sensors) radiated and accepted power curves' peaks for MO and NE have a mutual frequency ratio of 1.198. The use of NE in the model clearly results in a greater inaccuracy for the PD source location of 1.017 mm.

Index Terms—First peak (FP), extreme amplitude (EA), mineral oil (MO), natural ester (NE), partial discharge (PD), ultra-high frequency (UHF) sensor.

I. INTRODUCTION

The reliable operation of power transformers is vital for the security of the electrical power supply through the electrical grid. When strong electric fields are applied to an insulating material in a power transformer, the material partially short-circuits, resulting in a low-intensity electrical discharge known as a partial discharge (PD). Possible causes include deterioration brought on by natural ageing processes, manufacturing flaws that could induce early failure, and damage to the insulation from overvoltages and lightning strikes [1–2]. Continuous online monitoring, a high signal-to-noise ratio, resilience against external disturbances, and the ability to locate PD sources in three dimensions are some benefits of the ultra-high-frequency (UHF) method.

Predictive maintenance involves monitoring the PD activity levels inside transformers, as this can reveal internal faults that need to be addressed before the system is compromised. Locating sources of PD accurately in power transformers is of great importance for maintenance scheduling, maintenance efficiency, and even operational risk analysis. The time differences of arrival (TDOAs) of the signals at the various sensors can be used to localise the PD source when at least four sensors are mounted on the transformer's tank wall [3–4]. Numerous parameters, including transformer components and the distance between the PD source and UHF sensor, can influence the energy and waveform of a PD signal [5–7].

In [8], Dijkstra's algorithm using an artificial neural network (ANN) was developed and tested using a three-dimensional computer-aided design (CAD) model of a 300 MVA transformer with tank dimensions of 900 cm × 400 cm × 260 cm. Then, localisation errors of the algorithm, experiment, and simulation were compared using four UHF sensors. A deep learning (DL)-based approach was presented for the 3D localisation of PDs using three sensors within transformer tanks with dimensions of 1000 × 1000 × 500 mm³, 500 × 1000 × 500 mm³ and 2000 × 1000 × 1000 mm³ [9].

In [10], the distance-dependent attenuation in the simulation model was lower than that of the 300 MVA, 420 kV transformer experimental setup, which was expected because of fewer obstacles in the simulation model, but their distance-dependent attenuation characteristics were similar. In order to identify the locations on the tank wall where the UHF sensors could measure PD pulses from inside the winding with the highest sensitivity, simulations were conducted in [11] using a validated model of a three-phase 300 MVA, 420 kV power transformer in which artificial PD sources were placed inside the winding.

The simulated time-domain electromagnetic (EM) waveforms, their frequency spectra, and the attenuation characteristics of the EM waves as they propagated inside the tank or via transformer windings in [12] demonstrated good agreement with the results found experimentally. In [13], the propagation delay of the signal from each point in

the 3D space, which the transformer model contains, to the UHF sensors, was first obtained. The simulated signals' propagation delays were then compared with the measured signals, meaning that the PD location corresponds to the position where the simulated propagation time best approaches the measured data using a binary particle swarm optimisation algorithm. The shortest path method (i.e., Dijkstra's algorithm) in [14] is based on comparing the measured and database data. Detailed information on the transformer's internal components is required to create the database; in-service transformers do not have this information. Also, the hyperbolic method was solved in three different ways using the iterative algorithm, the Fang method, and the Chan method. The same 230/69 kV, 180 MVA power transformer, filled with oil, was used as in [13]. In [9–14], simulations were performed using CST Microwave Studio software.

The article [15] proposes a research method for detecting ultra-high-frequency partial discharge based on the induction signal of a transformer iron core. A finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) simulation experiment on the signal propagation process, enhancement, and extraction, as well as experimental validation using a 110 kV single-phase dual-winding transformer, was performed.

In [16], a solution based on the TDOA database is proposed to address the PD source localisation problem without the non-convergence problem. Helix 3D and the Microsoft Windows Presentation Foundation (.NET WPF) were used to model the transformer construction with simplified barriers. One experiment was conducted with a 110 kV power transformer, and the other was carried out with a platform for PD of electric power equipment.

In [17], a geometric model was used to analyse the cause of arrival time delay, and the XFDTD software was used to simulate the propagation of UHF waves through windings in order to investigate the feasibility of identifying PDs inside the winding using UHF methods. The measurement sensitivity and location accuracy of the UHF technique for PDs inside windings were tested on a 220 kV oil-immersed transformer.

A simulation model of a transformer with an acceptable simplification of core and windings was described in [18]. The FDTD approach was used to simulate the propagation of EM waves in transformers, and the waveform of the PD signals affected by the core and windings of varying sizes was reported. Two kinds of artificial insulation defects have been the subject of actual PD tests in a simulation transformer tank using the Hilbert fractal antenna. The design and development of a bio-inspired UHF sensor for PD detection in power transformers are described in [19]. Four distinct times of UHF propagation in a power transformer were simulated and illustrated.

In this paper, using Ansys HFSS software, which uses the finite element method (FEM), a typical power transformer model is made in order to analyse received PD signals at four UHF sensors and to localise the PD source using the first peak (FP) method. Two dielectric media are considered, i.e., mineral oil (MO) and natural ester (NE). Section II describes the simulation setup. In Section III, simulation results are presented and analysed for different electrical insulation media. Detailed comparisons of important parameters of the signals at the PD source and UHF sensors, and the calculated location of the PD source, are performed. Section IV comprises the most relevant facts and conclusions of this paper.

II. SIMULATION SETUP

The simulation model contains a small three-phase power transformer with a rated apparent power of 5 MVA and a rated transformation ratio of 66/11 kV. Secondly, it contains five dipole antennas, which serve as a PD source and four UHF sensors. The dimensions of the transformer tank are: length 2300 mm, width 880 mm, and height 2800 mm.

A. Simulation setup of the power transformer

Figure 1a shows the typical construction of a power transformer, which is being taken into account, consisting of:

- transformer tank made of stainless steel 304
- transformer insulating liquid, like MO or NE
- three-limb, four-stage (with 7 stages) magnetic core of the power transformer
- transformer three-phase low-voltage (LV) winding
- transformer three-phase high-voltage (HV) winding

It is assumed that the source of PDs is placed at point: S (1625, 340, 825) mm. It is located, counted from the bottom, between the lower part of the 10th disk of the LV winding and the upper part of the lower half of the 13th disk of the HV winding wound around the 3rd limb of the core; at approximately the middle of the lower half of the right core window, a little further forward when viewed from left to right in Figure 1a.

Figure 1a and Figure 1b illustrate, respectively, the side view and top view of the simulation model. The following are the adopted locations (centres of symmetry) for receiving UHF antennas (i.e., UHF sensors): U_1 (65, 65, 2750) mm, U_2 (1150, 440, 2758) mm, U_3 (2235, 815, 2755) mm, and U_4 (70, 810, 2760) mm. The largest possible distance in the tank is 3728.86 mm, which corresponds to an electromagnetic (EM) wave delay of 18.436 ns and 22.235 ns for MO and NE with dielectric permittivities of 2.2 and 3.2, respectively, in the empty transformer tank.

Figure 1c illustrates the dipole antenna used in the computer simulation for the PD source and the UHF antennas. The arms of the antenna have dimensions of 60 mm x 5 mm and are made of copper.

Figure 1: The metal tank of a power transformer with a three-limb magnetic core and three-phase windings, filled with MO or NE in: (a) side view, and (b) top view. (c) Dipole antenna used as PD source (S) and UHF sensors (U_1 , U_2 , U_3 , and U_4);

B. Limitations and approximations of the simulation setup of the power transformer

Because of the computer's limited capabilities (CPU, random-access memory (RAM), solid-state drive (SSD), and software), three-phase LV and HV windings must be simplified in comparison to the original design. Therefore, if the computer lacks sufficient capabilities, the likelihood of completing the simulation decreases as the number of model components grows.

The real insulation of the three-phase windings is considered to be approximately equal to the relative permittivity of the liquid dielectric (i.e., MO or NE) because all the paper insulation of the windings is impregnated with the liquid dielectric, thereby reducing the relative permittivity of the insulation. The LV and HV windings are made of 42 discs of the corresponding sizes. The copper from which the windings are made is approximated as a perfect electrical conductor (PEC).

The intermediate insulation between adjacent coils of LV or HV discs in the radial direction, 1.2 mm thick, is not taken into account; it is considered to be PEC. Although each HV disc should be made up of four sections along the vertical axis, it is split into two parts with a 1.2 mm gap. For an EM wave whose wavelength in MO and NE is equivalent to 20.23 cm and 16.77 cm, respectively, at a wave frequency of 1 GHz, an aperture of 1.2 mm is small; for lower wave frequencies, those wavelengths are proportionally greater. The strength of a signal beam passing through such an opening is dispersed in different directions with respect to the opening itself due to wave diffraction at such a small opening; that is, the beam's power decreases in the direction of the shortest possible distance to the corresponding UHF sensor. The real intermediate insulation between the LV and HV windings is considered to have the relative permittivity of MO or NE because the layers of pressboard insulation are also impregnated with dielectric liquid, thus reducing the relative permittivity of the pressboard.

Due to the lack of precise data and to avoid additional complications in modelling power transformer structures, the following less present and influential parts are not taken into account: a) insulating spacers, tapes, sleeves, etc., and b) metal core clamping frames, coil fixing parts, output leads on windings, screws, etc.

C. PD source and UHF sensors' modelling and PD source characteristics

Figure 2a illustrates the dipole antenna from Figure 1c, whose radiation is limited by a cube with a 500 mm side and a radiation boundary, to test the realised gain of the antenna. The dipole antenna's central point is located at the point (250, 250, 250) mm in relation to the origin of the Cartesian coordinate system. The excitation of the source of PDs is simulated as a broadband pulse with a minimum frequency of 0 Hz and a maximum frequency of 1 GHz, with a power of 1 W for the antenna realised gain analyses, and with an amplitude of 1 V in the simulations in Section III.

Figure 2b displays the transmitting antenna's radiated power and accepted power against frequency for the cube filled with MO or NE, with the antenna in the centre, from Figure 2a. It can be seen that the curve of radiated power is below the curve of accepted power in both cases. The maxima of the curves of radiated power and accepted power of the

dipole antenna are at 630 MHz and 755 MHz for the cube with NE and MO, respectively. The maxima of the curves of radiated power compared to the maxima of the curves of accepted power are smaller by 4.58 % and 3.62 % for the cubes with NE and MO, respectively.

Figure 2: (a) The dipole UHF antenna positioned in the centre of the cube with a side dimension of 500 mm, with transparent walls filled with MO or NE, to analyse its parameters. (b) Radiated power and accepted power of the dipole antenna versus frequency for the cube, filled with MO or NE, with the antenna in the centre, from Figure 2a.

Figures 3a-b, and Figures 4a-b show the far-field 3D polar diagrams and 2D rectangular plot contours, respectively, of the realised gain of a dipole UHF antenna expressed in decibels [dB], at a frequency of 1 GHz, for the antenna shown in Figure 1c and placed in the cube in the position shown in Figure 2a, when the dielectric liquid is MO or NE. From the blue areas to the red areas on the diagrams and plots, the realised gain changes from a minimum value to a maximum value.

It is evident from Figure 3a and Figure 3b that the realised gain pattern of the transmitting dipole antenna is not omnidirectional. The 3D diagrams appear more cubic than spherical in shape. In the x-y plane, the realised gain intensity is lowest along the longitudinal axis of the UHF transmitting antenna and within about $\pm 30^\circ$ of its centre. Also, the realised gain intensity is weaker along the vertical z-axis of the antenna's centre of symmetry. The highest realised gain intensities are on the shorter peak sides of these approximately rectangular 3D polar diagrams.

Figure 3: Corresponding 3D far-field polar diagram of the realised gain expressed in decibels [dB] of a dipole antenna placed in the centre of a cube with a side dimension of 500 mm and transparent walls, and filled with: (a) MO and (b) NE.

There is approximately a 33% shorter width of area in the middle of the rectangular plot contours with decreased realised gain, but up to 30.76% larger in that area, in Figure 4a for the cube with MO compared to Figure 4b for the cube with NE. On the other hand, the maximum realised gain of 3.96 dB is designated in Figure 4b for NE, which is a 25.32 % larger realised gain in relation to Figure 4a for the cube with MO, located on the shorter peak sides of the 3D plot diagrams in Figure 3.

When receiving UHF signals, the antenna's realised gain ability varies depending on the direction in space in similar ways for the two dielectric liquids.

Figure 4: Corresponding 2D far-field rectangular plot contour of the realised gain expressed in decibels [dB] of the dipole antenna positioned in the centre of the cube with a side dimension of 500 mm and transparent walls and filled with: (a) MO and (b) NE.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS AND ANALYSES IN THE CASES OF AN OLD AND A NEW LIQUID DIELECTRIC

In this section, results from the simulation made with the transformer model with PD source and four UHF sensors from Figure 1a are presented and explained in the cases of two liquid dielectrics, MO and NE. Firstly, the input pulses and output signals of the transmitting antenna (i.e., PD source) are considered. Secondly and thirdly, subjects of interest are, respectively, waveforms and spectra of the output signals of the receiving antennas (i.e., UHF sensors). Fourthly, the calculated results for the PD source location are compared in the cases of the two proposed liquid dielectrics in the power transformer model from Figure 1a.

A. Input pulses and output signals of the PD source antenna in the two liquid dielectrics from the Figure 1a model

Figure 5a shows the input pulses and output signals of the transmitting antenna in MO or NE in the transformer model from Figure 1a. Input pulses are Gaussian PD pulses with a minimum frequency of 0 Hz, a maximum frequency of 1 GHz, and an amplitude of 1 V. As can be seen, they are almost the same and overlap. On the other hand, the output signals of the antenna in MO and NE have broader first pulses with maxima that are 1.14 and 1.35 times delayed and 1.23 and 1.38 times lower, respectively, compared to their corresponding input pulses, and are oscillating, i.e., they last much longer. The output signal of the transmitting antenna in MO starts from the same moment, but in time is leading more and more compared to the output signal of the antenna in NE.

Figure 5b shows spectral diagrams of the output signals of the transmitting antenna at the same time interval [0.534–3.162] ns as its input pulses. They all have the same amplitude at about 165 MHz and 1 GHz. Spectral curves for input pulses approximately overlap. In the interval of [165–1000] MHz, the spectral curve for the output signal in NE is below all others. In the interval of [463–1000] MHz, the spectral curve for the output signal in MO is below the spectral curves for the input pulses.

Figure 5: (a) Input Gaussian PD pulses and output signals at the transmitting antenna for the power transformer model with MO or NE. (b) Corresponding amplitude spectra of the input pulses and output signals at the antenna.

B. Output signals recorded at UHF sensors 1, 2, 3, and 4 in the two liquid dielectrics from the Figure 1a model

Output signals recorded at UHF sensors 1, 2, 3, and 4 for the power transformer with MO (green curve) or NE (red curve) are shown in Figure 7a, Figure 7b, Figure 7c, and Figure 7d, respectively. It can be seen that the PD signals recorded in the power transformer model with NE have larger intensities and appear shifted on the x-axis to the right with similar waveforms, but amplitude peaks with different values, compared to the signals recorded in the power transformer model with MO using the same UHF sensors.

Figure 6: Output signals recorded at UHF sensors: (a) 1, (b) 2, (c) 3, and (d) 4 for the power transformer model with MO and NE, which are respectively designated with green and red curves.

From Figure 5a and Figure 6c, for the signal at sensor 3, it can be concluded that the first wave packet of the signal lasts approximately 10 ns, where the real moment of the signal's beginning is impossible to determine. It contains PD signals that arrive directly or most directly from the source. After that, only indirectly generated signals arrive at the UHF sensors. At sensors 1, 2, and 4, it is not so visible because of many more reflected waves.

For Signal 1 and Signal 4, in the model with NE, extreme amplitudes (EAs) that correspond to the EAs in the model with MO appear beyond the first wave packet lasting 10 ns, i.e., at 10.721 ns and 12.179 ns from their FPs, respectively; therefore, the interval of 12.179 ns will be used later in the paper as a reference because of the relevance of the results.

Figure 7a shows the FP amplitude vs FP time of appearance plot for the received PD signals at four UHF sensors originating from the same PD source set in two power transformer models filled with MO and NE, where the results are respectively designated with green and red points.

It is demonstrated that the FPs arrive in the following order: signal 2 arrives first, signal 3 second, signal 1 third, and signal 4 fourth. It can be calculated that the FPs of signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 at the corresponding sensors in the transformer model with NE arrive 1.1921, 1.1895, 1.1916, and 1.1953 times later compared to the transformer model with MO, respectively. Also, the FPs of signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 at the corresponding sensors in the model with NE are 1.8278, 1.6306, 1.8117, and 2.1298 times larger compared to the model with MO, respectively.

Signal 3 has an FP larger than the FPs of signals 1, 2, and 4 by -8.78, 4.194 and 7.234 and -8.703, 4.659 and 6.154 times for the models with MO and NE, respectively. Signal 4 arrives later than signals 1, 2, and 3 by 1.029 ns, 1.215 ns, and 1.157 ns and 1.027 ns, 1.209 ns and 1.153 ns for the models with MO and NE, respectively.

All mentioned proves that the waveforms of the corresponding signals in the two models are similar, but with larger intensity in the second model with NE compared to the first model with MO.

Figure 7b shows the EA vs EA time of appearance plot in the periods of 12.179 ns from the FPs of the signals, where results are designated respectively with green and red points, for the PD signals at four UHF sensors originating from the same PD source set in the power transformer model filled with MO and NE. It is evident that, in the period of 12.179 ns from the FP, EA of: signal 3 arrives first, signal 2 second, signal 1 third, and signal 4 fourth. It can be calculated that, in the given period, the EAs of signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 at the corresponding sensors in the transformer model with NE arrive 1.1882, 1.1845, 1.1799, and 1.1892 times later, respectively, compared to the transformer model with MO.

Additionally, the EAs of signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 at the corresponding sensors in the model with NE are 1.2326, 1.2003, 1.3304, and 1.3561 times larger, respectively, compared to the model with MO. These last-mentioned values are 1.4829, 1.3585, 1.3618, and 1.5705 less compared to the mutual ratios for the FPs of the signals from Figure 7a, which means that the influences of reflected waves on the resulting signals at the sensors have a larger increase over time in the model with MO.

Also, from Figure 7b, the EA of signal 3 appears before the EA of signal 2, unlike in Figure 7a, where the FP of signal 2 arrives before the FP of signal 3, which means that reflected waves are stronger at the sensor 2 location. Signal 3 has an EA larger than the EAs of signals 1, 2, and 4 by -1.317, -2.98, and 2.122 times and -1.421, -3.302, and 2.082 times for the models with MO and NE, respectively. Signal 4 arrives 1.07, 1.348, and 1.584 times and 1.071, 1.353, and 1.596 times later than signals 1, 2, and 3 for the models with MO and NE, respectively.

Figure 7: (a) FP amplitude vs FP time of appearance plot and (b) EA vs EA time of appearance plot in the periods of 12.179 ns from the FPs for the PD signals at four UHF sensors in the power transformer model filled with MO and NE, where results are designated respectively with green and red points.

C. Spectral diagrams of the output signals recorded at UHF sensors 1, 2, 3, and 4 in the two liquid dielectrics from the Figure 1a model

Figure 8a and Figure 8b show the S_{11} parameter for the PD source and S_{21} parameters for signals' transmissions between the PD source and UHF sensors 1-4 for the transformer models with (a) MO and (b) NE, respectively. It can be seen that the graphs of the S_{11} parameter and the S_{21} parameters are all shifted towards higher frequencies for the transformer model with MO compared to the same model with NE.

Figure 8: S_{11} parameter for the PD source and S_{21} parameters for signal transmissions between the PD source and UHF sensors 1-4 for the transformer models with (a) MO and (b) NE.

The minimum values of the S_{11} parameter for the PD source and the maximum values of the S_{21} parameters for signals transmitted between the PD source and UHF sensors 1-4 versus frequency are displayed in Figure 9. The results are indicated with green and red points, respectively, for the transformer models with MO and NE.

Figure 9: The minimum values of the S_{11} parameter for the PD source and the maximum values of the S_{21} parameters for signals transmitted between the PD source and UHF sensors 1-4 versus frequency, where the results are indicated with green and red points, respectively, for the transformer models with MO and NE.

In comparison with Figure 2b, where the maxima of the curves of radiated and accepted powers of the dipole antenna are at 755 MHz and 630 MHz for the cube with MO and NE, respectively, and the mutual ratio is 1.198, looking at Figure 9, the minima of the S_{11} parameter and maxima of the S_{21} parameters are also shifted to the right for the transformer model with MO in relation to the same model with NE, where the mutual ratios for the UHF sensors 1-4 are 1.202, 1.183, 1.212, 1.078, and 1.193, respectively.

Figures 10a-b show spectral diagrams of the signals at UHF sensors for the transformer model with MO in the periods (a) of 12.179 ns from the FPs, and (b) from the FPs to the ends of the signals' records at 45 ns. As can be seen, the maxima of signals 1 and 3 obviously decrease, and the maximum of signal 4 increases in their specific periods from the FPs to the ends of the signals' records, in comparison to the periods of 12.179 ns from the FPs' times of appearance of the signals.

Figure 10: Spectral diagrams of the signals at UHF sensors for the transformer model with MO in the periods (a) of 12.179 ns from the FPs, and (b) from the FPs to the ends of the signals' records. They are designated with green, blue, red, and black for signals 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively.

Figures 11a-b show spectral diagrams of the signals at UHF sensors for the transformer model with NE in the periods (a) of 12.179 ns from the FPs, and (b) from the FPs to the ends of the signals' records at 45 ns. It can be observed that the maximum of signal 3 obviously decreases, and the maxima of signals 1, 2, and 4 increase in their specific periods from the FPs to the ends of the signals' records, in comparison to the periods of 12.179 ns from the signals' FPs' times of appearance.

Figure 11: Spectral diagrams of the signals at UHF sensors for the transformer model with NE in the periods (a) of 12.179 ns from the FPs, and (b) from the FPs to the ends of the signals' records. They are designated with green, blue, red, and black for signals 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively.

In the periods of 12.179 ns from the signals' FPs and from the FPs to the ends of the signals' records at 45 ns, respectively, Figure 12 shows the weighted mean amplitudes vs weighted mean frequencies for signals 1-4 at the corresponding UHF sensors, measured from their spectral diagrams, where the results are designated for the transformer model with MO with green and light green colours and for the transformer model with NE with red and purple colours, respectively. From Figure 12, comparing results for the transformer model with NE, in the two periods from the signals' FPs, i.e., in 12.179 ns after them and until 45 ns, it is evident that the largest ratios of the weighted mean amplitudes of 1.777 and 1.616 are for signal 3 and signal 1, respectively. These ratios for signals 2 and 4 are smaller, at 1.26 and 1.18, respectively. This means that the influences of reflected waves on the received signals at sensors 3 and 1 are much smaller than at sensors 2 and 4. Considering ratios of the weighted mean frequencies of signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 in the two periods, which are 0.969, 1.015, 1.006, and 1.043, respectively, it can be concluded that reflected waves only slightly shift weighted mean frequencies of the signals, i.e., for signal 1 to the right by 18.736 MHz, and for signals 2, 3, and 4 to the left by 9.501 MHz, 4.009 MHz, and 27.856 MHz, respectively. Therefore, the largest frequency shift is for signal 4.

Figure 12: Weighted mean amplitudes vs weighted mean frequencies for signals 1-4 at the corresponding UHF sensors, obtained from their spectral diagrams. The results are given in relation to the type of liquid dielectric and the signals' periods from their FPs, for 12.179 ns after them or up to 45ns.

Comparing results for the transformer model with MO, in the two periods from the signals' FPs, i.e., in the 12.179 ns after them and until 45 ns, it can be observed that the largest ratios of the weighted mean amplitudes—1.701, 1.412, and 1.398—are for signals 3, 1, and 2, respectively. This ratio for signal 4 is much smaller, at 1.032. This means that the influence of reflected waves on the received signal at sensor 3 is larger than at sensors 2 and 1, and is much larger than at sensor 4. Considering the ratios of the weighted mean frequencies of signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 in the two periods, which are 1.003, 1.015, 1.043, and 1.05, respectively, it can be concluded that reflected waves only slightly shift the weighted mean frequencies of signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 to the left by 1.902 MHz, 11.42 MHz, 32.592 MHz, and 37.28 MHz, respectively. Therefore, the largest frequency shifts are for signals 4 and 3.

Comparing results for the transformer models with NE and MO, in the shorter periods from the signals' FPs, 12.179 ns after them, it can be seen that the ratios of the weighted mean amplitudes for signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 are 1.276, 1.106, 1.504, and 1.381, respectively. Therefore, in NE, signals reach larger weighted mean amplitudes than in MO within 12.179 ns after their FPs. The largest ratio is for signal 3, and the smallest one is for signal 2.

Comparing results for the transformer models with NE and MO, in the longer periods from the signals' FPs until 45 ns, it is demonstrated that the ratios of the weighted mean amplitudes for signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 are 1.115, 1.227, 1.439, and 1.207, respectively. Therefore, in NE, the signals reach larger weighted mean amplitudes than in MO in the periods from the signals' FPs to 45 ns. The largest ratio is for signal 3, and the smallest is for signal 1.

Ratios of the aforementioned ratios of the signals' weighted mean amplitudes in the two time periods, shorter and longer, for the transformer models with NE and MO, are 1.144, 0.902, 1.045, and 1.144. Considering these results, the relative changes of the ratios of the signals' weighted mean amplitudes in the two dielectrics and time periods are in the range of [-9.8–14.4] % in relation to the corresponding values in NE.

Comparing results for the transformer models with MO and NE in the shorter periods from the signals' FPs, 12.179 ns after them, it can be seen that the ratios of the weighted mean frequencies for signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 are 1.2005, 1.1678, 1.1994, and 1.1456, respectively. The weighted mean frequencies for signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 for the model with MO are 714.08 MHz, 775.35 MHz, 796.19 MHz, and 780.27 MHz, and for the model with NE, they are 594.81 MHz, 663.96 MHz, 663.8 MHz, and 681.12 MHz, respectively. Therefore, the signals reach [14.56–20.05] % higher weighted mean frequencies in the periods of 12.179 ns after the signals' FPs in MO in relation to the corresponding values in NE.

Comparing the results for the transformer models with MO and NE in the longer periods from the signals' FPs until 45 ns, it is demonstrated that the ratios of the weighted mean frequencies for signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 are 1.16076, 1.1673, 1.1573, and 1.1373, respectively. The weighted mean frequencies for signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 for the model with MO are 712.18 MHz, 763.93 MHz, 763.6 MHz, and 742.99 MHz, and for the model with NE, they are 613.54 MHz, 654.46 MHz, 659.79 MHz, and 653.26 MHz, respectively. Therefore, the signals reach [13.73–16.73] % higher weighted mean frequencies in the periods from the signals' FPs to 45 ns in MO in relation to the corresponding values in NE.

In the two time periods, shorter and longer, the maxima of the curves of radiated and accepted powers of the dipole antenna, which are at 630 MHz and 755 MHz in the cube with NE and MO, respectively, are in both of the obtained ranges of the corresponding weighted mean frequencies of the received signals at the UHF sensors. The ratios of the aforementioned ratios of the weighted mean frequencies for the transformer models with MO and NE in the two time periods are 1.0343, 1.0004, 1.0364, and 1.0072. Considering these results, the relative changes in the ratios of the signals' weighted mean frequencies in the two dielectrics and time periods are in the range of [0.04–3.64] % in relation to the corresponding values in NE.

D. PD source localisation in two cases of an old and a new liquid dielectric

Since four nonlinear equations with four unknown variables can be generated and solved, four sensors are adequate for the precise localisation of a PD source [3,6].

The TDOAs between the FPs of the respective signals at three UHF sensors in relation to the signal at the fourth reference UHF sensor were calculated using the FP method. In this manner, by examining the recorded signals in Figure 6 or Figure 7, the three TDOAs can be identified for each transformer model, i.e., the first one with MO and the second one with natural oil.

The time of arrival (TOA) of the signal at the reference sensor and the three coordinates of the PD source site are the four unknown values that must be ascertained in the FP method. These equations also contain fixed values, such as the 3D positions of the UHF sensors and the velocity of each UHF signal in MO, which is 20.23 cm/ns, and in NE, 16.77 cm/ns. To improve the likelihood of obtaining a substantial difference between the TOAs of PD signals at the sensors, every two UHF sensors should generally be placed far apart from one another.

Figure 13a shows the TDOAs of signals 1-4 in the two transformer models, that is, with MO and NE, using signal 1 as the reference.

From Figure 13a, it can be seen that the differences between the determined TDOAs in the two transformer models, i.e., with NE and MO, are unequal and always larger in absolute values for the model with NE. Looking from left to right, these differences are -0.4373 ns, -0.3027 ns and 0.1177 ns. Those values are reflected in the results of the PD source location in the two transformer models.

Figure 13b shows the calculated average absolute location errors of the PD source in the cases of different dielectric liquids, i.e., for the power transformer model with MO and NE, which are designated with green and red points, respectively. Evidently, the error is larger in the case of using NE in the model, by 1.017 mm.

Figure 13: (a) TDOAs of signals 1-4, taking signal 1 as the reference, in the two transformer models, i.e., with MO and NE. (b) Calculated average absolute location errors of the PD source for the power transformer models with MO and NE, which are designated with green and red points, respectively.

IV. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this paper is to generate PD signals from a PD source among metal windings that propagate to four UHF sensors, all of which are modelled as dipole antennas to analyse the results for detected signals in detail, and to calculate the location of the PD source from them using complex simulated 3D models of a power transformer in Ansys HFSS using two different liquid dielectrics (MO and NE) inside the transformer tank for comparison.

The propagation of EM waves from the source of PDs is very complex due to diffraction around and through the metal obstacles and multiple wave reflections in the power transformer. Simulations in Ansys HFSS were used to create graphical displays of received PD signals at UHF sensors, including the impacts of all signals' reflections and diffractions caused by the metal components of the transformer on their pathways from the PD source to the associated UHF sensors.

In contrast to the Ansys HFSS simulations, the location and type of the PD source in a real power transformer in the field are unknown, and we only know that it is a point source with uniform radiation in all directions. On the other hand, in the Ansys HFSS model, the drawbacks of the simulations are that the LV and HV windings are somewhat simplified, less important parts are ignored, and the PD source and UHF sensors are shaped like dipole antennas. This indicates that the source of PDs is not a point, meaning that it does not radiate with the same intensity in every direction, which affects the forms and the intensities of the signals that are received at various locations where the sensors are located, compared to the case when a real PD source exists.

The main conclusions in this paper are:

- In the experimental cube with the used antenna in its centre, the maximum realised gain reaches 4 dB with NE in the cube, which is 25 % larger in relation to the realised gain that reaches 3.2 dB in the cube filled with MO, and it is located on the shorter peak area sides of the 3D plot diagrams.
- In the typical transformer model, when comparing the NE model to the MO model, the FPs and the EAs of signals 1-4 at the corresponding sensors are respectively [1.6306–2.1298] and [1.2003–1.3561] times larger, with the lowest in signal 2 and the highest in signal 4. This indicates that the influence of reflected waves on the received signals at the sensors has a greater increase over time in the model with MO.
- In the shorter periods from the signals' FPs, at 12.179 ns after them, and in the longer periods from the signals' FPs until 45 ns, it can be seen respectively that:
 - Comparing results for the transformer models with NE in relation to MO, the ratios of the weighted mean amplitudes for signals 1-4 are in the sets of [1.106–1.504] and [1.115–1.439], where the largest ratio is for signal 3 in both cases, and the smallest one is for signal 2 in the first case and for signal 1 in the second case. Therefore, in NE, signals reach larger weighted mean amplitudes than in MO in both periods.
 - Comparing results for the transformer models with MO in relation to those with NE, the ratios of the weighted mean frequencies for signals 1-4 are in the sets [1.1456–1.2005] and [1.1373–1.1673], where the largest ratio is for signal 1 in the first case and for signal 2 in the second case, and the smallest one is for signal 4 in both cases. In the two time periods, shorter and longer, the maxima of the curves of radiated and accepted powers of the dipole antenna, which are at 630 MHz and 755 MHz in the cube with NE and MO, respectively, are in both of the obtained ranges of the corresponding weighted mean frequencies of the received signals at the UHF sensors in the typical power transformer model. The graphs in the full period of the S_{11} source parameter and

the S_{21} parameters between the source and corresponding UHF sensors 1-4 are all shifted together toward higher frequencies for the transformer model with MO compared to the same model with NE.

- Absolute values of the calculated TDOAs are always greater for the NE transformer model compared to the model with MO. The minimum mutual difference of TDOAs in absolute values is 0.1177 ns between sensors 4 and 1, and the maximum of 0.4373 ns is between sensors 2 and 1. The outcomes of the two transformer models' PD source location reflect those values. The use of NE in the model results in a greater inaccuracy of 1.017 mm compared to when MO is used.

In the simulation, it was not possible to set all properties of the NE and MO, and the obtained results depend on them. Properties that were able to be set according to the literature for NE and MO were: relative permittivity (3.2 and 2.2), bulk conductivity ($4.31 \cdot 10^{-10}$ S/m and $6.25 \cdot 10^{-10}$ S/m), dielectric loss tangent (0.0036 and 0.003), and mass density (920 kg/m^3 and 890 kg/m^3). These properties vary according to the state and the type of the dielectric liquids in reality (whether they are new or after years of exploitation in a power transformer in operation in a plant, the sort of NE, etc.), but in the simulation, it was only possible to set one value for NE and MO for each parameter. Some characteristic parameters like viscosity, PD inception voltage, dielectric strength, etc., could not be set.

Physical explanations of the behaviours of the UHF PD EM waves' propagation and the received signals at sensors 1-4 in the typical power transformer model, according to the set enabled parameters of the dielectric liquids in the simulation, could be as follows:

- Influences of the higher dielectric constant of NE compared to that of MO are:
 - The higher electric field stress concentrations at the PD source, which lead to more intense discharges
 - The lower velocity of each UHF signal, which is 20.23 cm/ns in MO and 16.77 cm/ns in NE
 - Higher reflection and refraction, which cause multipath propagation and distortion of the original pulse shape
- UHF PD EM waves are generally stronger at the sensor when propagating through NE compared to MO because of the higher permittivity and lower streamer velocity characteristic of NE, which results in more energetic, high-frequency discharges. Higher relative permittivity in the dielectric fluid generally enhances the capacitive coupling of the PD source, allowing more charge to flow in the discharge streamer. This higher charge separation produces a stronger EM radiated emission, which is what the UHF sensor detects.
- The higher permittivity, combined with a higher dielectric loss factor ($\tan \delta$) in natural esters, also leads to greater attenuation of the UHF signal as it travels from the source to the sensor, thereby reducing the signal-to-noise ratio. UHF PD EM waves exhibit higher intensity at UHF sensors in NE than in MO for the same voltage and source shape because NE produces more intense PD events (higher charge magnitude) despite higher dielectric loss. The increase in energy produced by the more intensive discharge in NE, compared to MO, more than compensates for increased signal absorption over the propagation path to the sensor.
- The higher density inhibits the rapid movement of charges during the pre-breakdown stage, which can lead to a more concentrated, violent discharge (higher peak energy) before the streamer traverses the gap, especially at high temperatures.
- The TDOAs of PD signals at UHF sensors 1-4 are generally larger in NE than in MO due to the higher relative permittivity of NE, which causes EM waves to travel more slowly and follow more complex, delayed paths. It alters the direct path, often forcing the signal to take longer, reflected paths to the sensor. NE leads to higher inaccuracies in TOA and TDOA calculations and directly compromises the accuracy of standard UHF localisation techniques.

In the simulations, there is no measuring device (oscilloscope), as in real measurements used to record the signals at a UHF sensor, so there is no error in the arrival times of the signals at the sensor due to the limited resolution of the signal sampling when converting them from analogue to digital form. Also, no background noise sources are taken into account.

In this paper, the calculations are not validated by actual measurements on a power transformer with the same construction. A high-power pulse generator or an antenna must be used as the artificial source in order to conduct such tests on a real experimental power transformer, which is challenging to temporarily install in the windings because of their intricate, solid structure and to provide two different liquid dielectrics in the tank for two special experiments. Furthermore, the UHF sensors would not be able to align with the directions of the strongest EM waves since they would be stationary.

At the end, it is important to emphasise that these simulations are a great way to analyse the waveforms, amplitudes, spectra, and attenuations of PD signals at four UHF sensors in the power transformer model. They are also a great way to set the PD source in the model and check the errors of its calculated location after the analysis of the simulations' results. Furthermore, it is much simpler to place the UHF sensors in the model when two different liquid dielectrics are taken into consideration in the tank, one after the other, to get comparable results.

The waveforms of the corresponding signals at sensors 1-4 in the two power transformer models are of similar shape, but with different amplitude spectra in the two time periods, with higher intensity and shifted to the left in the second model with NE compared to the first model with MO. In the context of PD signals' detection at UHF sensors 1-4, their FPs and EAs, in the periods of 12.179 ns after corresponding FPs, emerged later and with greater magnitudes when employing NE as the transformer's liquid dielectric compared to MO. Therefore, in the power station or transformer station, those signals will be simpler to detect at the four UHF sensors and easier to use for, but not necessarily more accurate, PD source localisation in the power transformer with NE than with MO.

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